

Guangdong, Jiangsi, Zhejiang, and Fukien. In 1984, the hybrid was named Wei You 64 and was planted on 0.26 million ha in China.

Wei You 64 yielded about 1 t/ha more than conventionally bred Xian Ai Zhao 9 in national yield trials in the South Yangtze Valley (Table 2). It matured in 124 d. Wei You 64 yielded the same as Wei You 6 but matured 12 d earlier (Table 3). Its short duration allows a second crop planting as late as 1 Aug without significant yield loss. If planted that late, Wei You 6 yields only 3 t/ha. Highest yield of Wei You 64 in China has been 11.3 t/ha.

Wei You 64 is resistant to blast, bacterial blight, brown planthopper (BPH), and green leafhopper and moderately resistant to yellow dwarf virus in China. It yields more seed (1.5-2.5 t/ha) than Wei You 6 (1-2 t/ha) because its male parent produces more pollen. Wei You 64 is susceptible to sheath blight, and therefore unsuitable for waterlogged soils. It is moderately resistant to lodging.

Table 1. Performance of V20A/IR9761-1-19-1-64 (Wei You 64) and Wei You 6 in regional yield trials (second crop) in Hunan, China, 1982.

Hybrid	Trials (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Growth duration (d)	Productivity (kg/ha per d)
V20A/IR9761-19-1-64	17	6.1	101	57
Wei You 6	17	5.1	125	41

Table 2. Performance of Wei You 64 and Xian Ai Zhao 9 in national yield trials (first crop) in China, 1984.

Hybrid	Trials (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Growth duration (d)	Productivity (kg/ha per d)
Wei You 64	14	1.7	124	62
Xian Ai Zhao 9	14	6.8	119	57

Table 3. Performance of Wei You 64 and Wei You 6 in national yield trials (one crop) in China, 1984.

Hybrid	Trials (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Growth duration (d)	Productivity (kg/ha per d)
Wei You 64	10	1.8	124	63
Wei You 6	10	1.9	136	58

V20A/IR9761-19-1 also has shown promise in trials in Indonesia, India, and Korea. At IRRI, however, its yields are

limited by tungro, ragged stunt, and grassy stunt 2, and by BPH biotype 2. *ℓ*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DROUGHT TOLERANCE

Developing closely related rice lines with different drought-induced abscisic acid (ABA) accumulation

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ABA is a plant hormone that mediates plant responses to drought stress. It causes stomata to close, thus reducing transpirational water losses. Differences in the ability of plants to accumulate ABA could affect their ability to withstand drought.

To objectively evaluate the consequences of differences in drought-induced ABA accumulation (DIAA) on survival or yield ability during drought, genetic stocks with contrasting DIAA but similar characteristics are required. We screened several rices for DIAA using a test in which leaves were

Characteristics of F₄ plants of two rice crosses and plants of the parental genotypes. ^a

	ABA content (ng/g fresh weight)	Leaf fresh weight (mg)	Plant height at maturity (cm)	Days to panicle emergence from sowing
			<i>IR20/63-83</i>	
Low-ABA selections (n=12)	391	455	64.8	90.2
High-ABA selections (n=21)	814***	398 ^{ns}	17.9*	91.0 ^{ns}
63-83(n=6)	428	629	100.5	85.3
IR20 (n=6)	909***	190***	41.8***	85.0 ^{ns}
			<i>IR20/IR36</i>	
Low-ABA selections (n=15)	606	206	54.2	84.2
High-ABA selections (n=22)	844***	181 ^{ns}	52.2 ^{ns}	83.5 ^{ns}
IR36 (n=3)	512	185	51.3	86.7
IR20 (n=3)	919*	110***	38.1**	93.0 ^{ns}

^a Plants were grown in a glasshouse at Cambridge, U. K. *, ** and *** indicate significant differences at $P < 0.05$, 0.01 and 0.001, respectively, between low- and high-ABA selections and between parental genotypes; ns = not significant. ^b Leaf six for IR20/63-83 and leaf five for IR20/IR36.

detached and rapidly water-stressed. ABA concentrations were determined in

leaf extracts using a gas-liquid chromatograph fitted with a pulse-

ABA content (ng/g fresh wt), F₄ or S₂ family mean

ABA content (ng/g fresh wt), F₄ family mean

ABA content (ng/g fresh wt), F₄ or S₂ family mean

Relation between (A) mean ABA concentrations of water-stressed leaves of the F₄ and F₃ (S₂ and S₁ generations for parents) of the cross IR20/6343; (B) mean ABA concentrations of F₄ (or S₂) and leaf fresh weight of F₄ (or S₂) of the cross IR20/6343; (C) mean ABA concentrations of the F₄ and F₃ of the cross IR20/IR36. Data points are means of 6-8 leaves and bars indicate 2 × S. E. mean. Lines of best fit for the regression of y on x are shown. Open symbols represent parents or lines selected for low ABA; closed symbols, for high ABA. F₄ families with the same symbol were derived from common F₃ families. Regression coefficients (r) and slopes (β) are indicated.

modulated electron capture detector. Cultivars that contrasted most in DIAA were crossed and their progeny screened and selected for differences in DIAA in F₂ to F₄.

The progeny of two crosses were examined in detail. In IR20/63-83 (lowland/ upland), the parents differed about threefold in DIAA. IR20 leaves produced about 940 ng ABA/g fresh weight after 2 h stress, and 63-83 produced about 316 ng. F₂ plants of the cross had a continuous range of DIAA between that of the parents. Because of a high negative correlation between DIAA and leaf size (fresh or dry weight) ($r =$

4.47; $P < 0.001$) at F₂, only those lines in which DIAA was apparently unrelated to leaf size were studied in detail.

For them, DIAA at F₃ was significantly correlated with DIAA at F₂ ($r = 0.89$; $P < 0.02$). At F₄ there also was good DIAA heritability (Fig. 1A). Leaf size and DIAA still were associated (Fig. 1B), but some lines had similar-sized leaves but different DIAA.

In IR20/ IR36 (lowland/ lowland), the correlation between DIAA at F₃ and DIAA at F₂ was poor ($r = 0.28$; $P > 0.05$). However, by selecting only the more extreme types at F₃, heritability of DIAA was improved in the next

generation (Fig. 1C). There was no correlation between DIAA and leaf size.

For the progeny from both crosses, differences in leaf fresh weight and height between the high and low ABA lines were much smaller than the corresponding differences between parental genotypes (see table).

There were no differences in mean flowering dates of different ABA groups. Thus, these selections will be suitable for determining the effects of different DIAA on plant growth and yield under drought, without confounding the results by having large differences in morphology and phenology. *ℓ*